

Principal's Support In Implementing Reading Intervention Program And Its Influence On The Performance Of Struggling Learners

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Abstract

Effective school leadership is vital for fostering students' academic and personal development. Principals who provide strong support are instrumental in the successful implementation of educational programs. Such leadership enhances teachers' instructional practices, whereas a lack of support can impede program success. This study focused on the principal's support in implementing reading intervention program and its influence on the performance of struggling learners focusing in integrated schools in Lake Sebu Districts, Schools Division of South Cotabato. The specific objectives were to determine the extent of principals' support in implementing reading intervention program; describe the reading performance of learners, determine the relationship between the principal support and reading performance of learners and determine the significant difference between the pretest and post-test of struggling learners. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered through researcher – made survey questionnaire and analyzed the prevailing relationships between variables. The findings revealed that respondents agreed that principal supports all components of the reading intervention program. Despite this support across these components, the reading performance of learners showed minimal improvement from pretest to post-test and majority of the learners were identified as Instructional level. Statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship was found between the principals' support in implementing reading intervention program and the learner's reading performance. Furthermore, pretest and post-test score reveal a significant improvement in learners' reading performance following the implementation of a reading intervention program. The study concludes that while principal support is essential, other factors may also influence the effectiveness of reading intervention programs on student outcomes. Recommendations include exploring additional variables that may impact reading performance and continue support the implementation of reading intervention program to help and improve the performance of learners who are struggling in reading.

Keywords: *Principal's Support, Reading Intervention Program, Struggling learners.*

INTRODUCTION

School leadership is crucial for students' academic and personal growth, with principals' support essential for effective program implementation. Supportive leadership enhances teachers' instructional practices, while a lack of it, hinders program success. Principals should implement programs that cater to the needs of all learners and support teachers for they are the one who put plans into action. As mentioned by Park et al. (2018) supportive leadership is key to improving teaching practices and learners' outcomes.

Research underscores the significant role of school leadership in improving schools and fostering student success. Leithwood, Aitken, and Jantzi (2006), cited in Morris et al. (2019) highlight the influence of leadership behaviors on school improvement. Leithwood, Sun, and Schumacker (2019) further confirm that school leadership greatly impacts learners' academic achievement and personal growth, and Rocamora (2021) adds that positive school experiences shape children's future outcomes. The study by Daycoras (2023) identified key forms of support provided by school principals, including policy implementation, teacher involvement, collaboration with stakeholders, and access to learning spaces and resources in Panabo City, Davao Del Norte.

UNESCO (2021) reports that early learning delays often persist and worsen over time. The COVID-19 pandemic intensified issues like student distress, resource shortages, and learning gaps (Kuhfeld & Tarasawa, 2020), with temporary school closures causing significant learning losses (Schult et al., 2022). Kennedy and Strietholt (2023) also mentioned that school closure has a significant and substantial negative effect on learners' reading performance. Additionally, Adigun et al. (2021) found reduced reading engagement among secondary school students in Nigeria.

In Philippine context, the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results showed that 15-year-old Filipino students ranked last in reading comprehension among 79 nations. Challenges persist as many Filipinos struggle with reading and basic math (San Juan, 2019). Idulog et al. (2023) highlights the need for improvement in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and critical thinking skills. A study in Northern Mindanao also found high frustration levels and a significant number of non-readers among students (Ong, Tagluco, & Fermano, 2021).

Recognizing the challenges in literacy, the Department of Education (DepEd) introduced the 'Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa' (3Bs) initiative through DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019. This initiative urges all DepEd offices to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and to nurture a culture of reading (DepEd, 2019).

In 2022, the Department of Education (DepEd) SOCCSKSARGEN developed the Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan (LRCP) through Region Memorandum No. 271, s. 2022. This plan outlines strategies, initiatives, and innovations to ensure the continuous delivery of basic education and address learning gaps resulting from the pandemic.

In 2023, DepEd introduced additional frameworks to further address learning gaps. DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023, titled "Adoption of the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP)," aims to strengthen learning recovery efforts and improve numeracy and literacy. This was followed by DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2023, which provides policy guidelines for the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC). The NLC designed to improve learning outcomes and strengthen teacher competence (DepEd, 2023).

Based on literature review, majority of the studies conducted focused on international studies (Morris et al., (2019); Park et al., (2018); Manickavagasam, (2018); Lynch, (2019), while in Philippine context (Dayrocas, (2023). However, there is lack of studies conducted in South Cotabato province, particularly in Lake Sebu East District and in Lake Sebu West District.

In reference to the consolidated pretest reports for Grade 7 English Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for the school 2023-2024 school year, conducted in eight integrated schools in Lake Sebu East District and three in Lake Sebu West District, 222 learners were independent level, 278 learners were at the instructional level, 107 were at the frustration level, and 59 were identified as non-readers out of a total of 666 learners tested

It is in this light that the researcher assessed the principal' support in implementing reading intervention programs and its influence on the performance of struggling learners about different factors that affect it. The findings of the study may serve as baseline data for administrators of educational policies for future decision-making.

Statement of the Problem

The primary concern of this study was to assess the extent of principal's supports in implementing reading intervention program and its influence on the performance of struggling learners in Lake Sebu East and Lake Sebu West Distrits. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of principal's support on the implementation of intervention program for struggling learners in terms of:
 - 1.1 Time - allocation and Scheduling
 - 1.2 Approaches and Strategies
 - 1.3 Information and Communication Technology kills
 - 1.4 Learning Resources
 - 1.5 Teaching Material Support
 - 1.6 Training of Teachers
 - 1.7 Performance Tracking
 - 1.8 Stakeholder's Involvement
2. What is the reading performance result of the struggling learners?
 - 2.1 Pretest
 - 2.2 Post - test
3. Is there a significant relationship between principal's support in implementing reading intervention program for struggling learners and their reading performance?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and post-test of the struggling learners?

Hypotheses

This study aimed to test these hypotheses to gain insight into the role of leadership in the effectiveness of educational interventions.

1. There is no significant relationship between principal's support in implementing reading intervention program for struggling learners and their reading performance.
2. There is no significant difference between the pretest and post-test of the struggling learners.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study was designed to determine the extent of principal's support in implementing reading intervention program and its influence on the performance of struggling learners. The study employed a descriptive correlational research design using self – made questionnaire that was validated by five (5) panel of experts. According to McBurney and White (2009), descriptive - correlational design is used to create static representations of circumstances as well as establish the link between distinct variables.

Ninety - seven (97) high school teachers served as respondents selected using proportional stratified sampling. The survey questionnaire undergone Cronbach Alpha testing to ensure its reliability. Data were analyzed utilizing frequency and percentage count, mean weighted average Pearson Product Correlation and t-test.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the Lake Sebu East and Lake Sebu West Districts in Lake Sebu, South Cotabato. The municipality has two districts headed each by District Supervisor. The Lake Sebu East District is composed of eight (8) integrated schools, while the Lake Sebu West District comprises three (3) integrated school with the total of 11 (eleven) integrated schools. Each school implements various reading interventions to evaluate learners' reading performance and Phil-IRI being one of the tools used for assessment.

In terms of topography and landscapes, the locations of some schools are very accessible to any form of transportation and some schools are reachable through motorcycle ride or known as *habal – habal*. The land area is agricultural land where most people are farmers and occupied by mostly T'boli and Ubo people. The setting was chosen since the researcher has been working as a high school teacher in one of the districts and there were limited studies conducted about principal's support in implementing reading intervention program and its influence on the performance of struggling learners. The different schools had identified learners belong to instructional level, frustration level and non- readers.

Respondents of the Study

The population is the collection of all the units to whom the findings of the research are to be applied (Shukla, 2020). The population of interest for the study consists of the primary group on which the research is focused, along with any other individuals, dyads, groups, organizations, or other entities that one wishes to understand and to whom or to which the study results may be generalized or transferred (Casteel & Bridier, 2021).

The respondents were ninety - seven (97) junior high school permanent teachers in integrated schools of Lake Sebu East and Lake Sebu West Districts, Lake Sebu, South Cotabato with at least one (1) year of the length of their employment.

Sampling Technique

Simkus (2023) defined sampling is the process of drawing statistical conclusions from a subset of the population. Stratified random sampling involves dividing the population into subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics. In this study stratified random sampling procedure was used for selecting the respondents. Samples are then randomly selected from each stratum to ensure representation of all subgroups. This technique was utilized to ensure a fairly equal representation of the variables for the study.

The stratification was based on schools in Lake Sebu Districts in Lake Sebu South Cotabato. Within each school, selection of respondents was by simple random sampling.

Data Gathering Instrument

The respondent's profile was gathered using the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of the following sections: first section dealt with the teacher's profile and the last section highlighted the principal's support in implementing reading intervention program.

The Evaluation Tool for the support of the principal includes: Time -Allocation and Scheduling, Approaches and Strategies, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Skills, Learning Resources, Teaching Material Support, Training of Teachers, Performance Tracking and Stakeholder Involvement.

The research instrument was subjected to content validation through 5 – panel validity test. Subsequently, pilot testing was done to enhancing the reliability, validity, and practicality of questionnaires (Wadood et al., 2021). The validity was based on the content, usability, and consistency of the research instruments.

In this study, the researcher used Likert scale to measure the support of principal in implementing reading intervention program rating scale description to assess their overall score. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to test the reliability and validity of the modified survey questionnaire. Based on the calculated data, it is clear that the survey questionnaire is reliable and valid with rating 0.94 which implies that the level of reliability and validity is excellent.

Data Gathering Procedure

After making final draft of research instrument, the permission of the Graduate School to conduct the study was secured. Subsequently, upon securing the request from Dean of the Graduate School, a letter request was forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of South Cotabato. When the request was granted, similar letter was drafted and sent to the District Supervisors and School Heads for recommendation.

After securing the endorsement, the researcher personally distributed printed copies of questionnaire scrutinize by panel of experts to every respondent. The researcher waited ten (10) days before gathering the answered questionnaires and encoded it for interpretation.

Statistical Treatment

The researcher gathered the data, and the responses from the accomplished questionnaires were properly encoded, processed, and analyzed. The following statistical treatment were applied by the researcher in order to properly interpret the data. The data were computed using the

appropriate statistical tools such as Average Weighted Mean, Frequency Count and Percentage, Pearson Product Moment of Correlation and t-test.

The Likert scale was used to determine the extent of principal's support in implementing intervention program for struggling learners. Weighted mean average will be used for interpretation.

The frequency count and percentage calculation were used to describe the reading performance level of learners in the result of Phil – IRI.

To test the significant relationship between principal's support in implementing reading intervention program for struggling learners and their reading performance, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson -r) was used.

This study also used t-test to determine if there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of struggling of the struggling learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 1,2,3,4,5,6,7, and 8 shows the extent of principal's support in implementing reading intervention program in terms of Time -Allocation and Scheduling, Approaches and Strategies, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Skills, Learning Resources, Teaching Material Support, Training of Teachers, Performance Tracking and Stakeholder Involvement.

Table 1

Time – Allocation and Scheduling

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Implements the prepared and approved class schedule.	4.52	0.70	Strongly Agree
Ensures the school-based activities including reading interventions scheduled during open hours to minimize disruption of regular classes.	4.27	0.63	Strongly Agree
Ensures that the allocated time for reading intervention is adequate to address learners' learning gap.	4.04	0.76	Agree
Allows the utilization of open periods for reading intervention sessions.	4.08	0.68	Agree
Encourages the flexible scheduling of reading intervention sessions including option during weekends and summer break, based on learners and teacher's availability.	4.00	0.72	Agree
Section Mean	4.18	0.53	Agree

Results on Table 1 reveal the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of Time – Allocation and Scheduling is described as “agree “with a mean of 4.18 with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.53$. The overall finding implies that respondents are agree with the principal's level of support on the implementation of reading intervention program in terms of time - scheduling and allocation.

Additionally, respondents “strongly agree” that principal implements the prepared and approved class schedule as stipulated in Region Memorandum CLMD no.271, s. 2022 and ensures the school-based activities including reading interventions scheduled during open hours to minimize disruption of regular classes.

According to Manickavasagam (2018), adequate and uninterrupted time is essential in schools. Reading instruction requires sufficient uninterrupted time for effectiveness. Also, Schult et al. (2022) proposed that when students have more free time, they tend to spend more of it reading. Furthermore, children who are struggling should be given extra instructional time to catch up.

Table 2
Approaches and Strategies

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Promotes the use of online platforms such as ZOOM, Google meet and other social media platforms for reading intervention, especially in situations where face – to – face sessions are not feasible.	3.13	1.04	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Prefers face – to - face reading intervention to address the learners’ gap in reading.	4.53	0.60	Strongly Agree
Provides audio and videos materials to be utilized during intervention to address learning gaps.	3.84	0.81	Agree
Supports the implementation of versatile intervention strategies including digital and in – person platforms to cater the diverse learning needs.	3.91	0.71	Agree
Ensures that the school materials used during intervention are arranged in ways that are clear and consistent.	3.93	0.84	Agree
Section Mean	3.87	0.58	Agree

As indicated in the above table, the extent of principal’s support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of Approaches and Strategies got the mean of 3.87 described as the respondents “agree” with the support given by the principal with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.58$. It can be gleaned from the table above that respondents strongly agree on the support given by the principal on implementation of face – to - face reading intervention rather than the support given on the use of online platforms when face – to – face sessions are not feasible where respondents were neither agree or disagree with the mean of 3.13.

As specified in Region Memorandum CLMD no.271, s. 2022, both online and in-person interventions are available options to put intervention strategies into action (DepEd, 2022). Endo (2024) states that by applying effective reading intervention approaches and strategies in classrooms allow students the opportunity to experience the success and even joy through their reading.

Table 3
Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Skills

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Assigned trained teachers in using Educational Technologies	4.00	0.00	Agree
Provides teacher various remedial materials on different platforms.	3.85	0.74	Strongly Agree
Allow teachers to attend trainings and seminars to hone their skills on using Educational Technologies.	4.34	0.69	Strongly Agree
Ensure that there are available Educational Technologies such as computers and television that can be used during intervention and remedial.	4.04	0.82	Agree
Encourages teachers to utilize Educational Technologies to support teaching and learning.	4.25	0.72	Strongly Agree
Section Mean	4.09	0.48	Agree

Table 3 presents the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of ICT Skills described as "agree" with the mean of 4.09 with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.48$. The finding reflects that the principals support on the use of ICT in conducting the intervention for learning. The mean score suggests a positive response of the principal. It is also shown that the respondents strongly agree that principal provides materials on different platform and allow teachers to attend training and seminar to develop teacher's skills on using Educational Technologies.

Dean et al. (2021) state that one way to offer reading support is by utilizing information and communication technology (ICT) programs and there are many different technological tools available to assist children in improving their reading, spelling, and language skills. Although not all studies have positive outcomes on the use of ICT to reading according to Campuzano et al. (2009), cited in Dean et al. (2021), reviews suggest that many ICT programs lead to improvements reading skills of learners.

Table 4
Learning Resources

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Full utilization of MELCS (Most Essential Learning Competencies) based learning resources are applied.	4.63	0.57	Strongly Agree
Teacher – made learning resources are being develop to address the shortage of modules in certain subject areas.	4.14	0.75	Agree
Conducts a regular inventory of learning resources to ensure availability and alignment with intervention needs.	3.85	0.78	Agree
Proper selection of utilization of accessible learning resources.	3.94	0.67	Agree
Maximize the use of available modules as support and aid to additional enrichment activities at home.	4.13	0.59	Agree
Section Mean	4.14	0.52	Agree

As collated based on the answers gathered; Table 4 revealed the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of learning resources which got a mean of 4.14, described as "agree" with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.52$. This suggests that principals support the importance of providing the necessary learning resources to support the program effectively. It also shown that participants strongly agree on the support of the principal in full utilization of MELCS (Most Essential Learning Competencies) based learning resources are applied.

The findings reflect the compliance of the schools in the DM NO. 89, S. 2020, instructed school to refer to the MELCs in creating learning activity sheets, self-learning modules, and other instructional materials DepEd, 2020).

As noted in the study by Idulog et al. (2023), the lack of resources is one of the key reasons contributing to low reading abilities. Sambayon et al. (2023) suggest that contextualizing materials can capture learners' interest ensuring all learners stay engaged in the learning process.

Table 5
Teaching Material Support

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Ensures that the teaching materials used during intervention and remediation are quarterly developed by reading and writers experts.	3.77	0.85	Agree
Ensures that there is a regular update of materials provided by reading and writers experts.	3.81	0.79	Agree
Provides available reading materials by reading and writers experts in school.	3.79	0.81	Agree
Provides available Manuals for Teaching Reading that are appropriate for the context and culture in school.	3.97	0.83	Agree
Ensures that the assessment tools used in intervention are developed or validated by reading specialist to maintain quality and relevance.	3.80	0.81	Agree
Section Mean	3.83	0.70	Agree

Table 5 presents the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of Teaching Material Support. As shown in the table, the answers revealed a total mean of 3.83, described as agree with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.70$. This implies that the teaching material for reading intervention program are supported by the principals. Principals ensure that materials used were developed by expert or specialist.

As stated by DepEd (2022) in Region Memorandum CLMD no. 271, s. 2022, the Manual for Teaching Reading is suitable to the context and culture of region 12. Teaching materials were developed through collaboration between the reading specialists, teachers, and supervisors, alongside the Regional Office, under the guidance of reading consultants (DepEd, 2022). According to the study by Idulog et al. (2023), developing reading materials that are both engaging and culturally relevant to Filipino students can significantly enhance their reading abilities.

Table 6
Training for Teachers

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Ensures that teachers have solid grasp of the reading materials.	4.12	0.69	Agree
Ensures that teacher/s regularly attends training on conducting reading intervention enhancement.	4.12	0.79	Agree
Ensures that trained teachers conduct reading intervention program in school.	4.10	0.77	Agree
Ensures that trained teachers assess the reading performance of learners.	4.16	0.72	Agree
Ensures that trained teachers applied reading intervention programs in school.	4.09	0.78	Agree
Section Mean	4.12	0.63	Agree

It is reflected in Table 6, that extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of training for teachers got a mean rating of 4.12 described as agree with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.63$. This implies that the principal ensures that teachers attend training before implementation and administering reading intervention program. As stated in The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual 2018, teachers who will administer the Phil-IRI should read the manual thoroughly.

As DepEd (2019) escalate the conduct of School – based Learning Action Cell (SLAC) to provide trainings and allow teachers to enhance their reading fluency, comprehension, and teaching skills.

Fuchs et al. (2012) as cited by McMaster (2021), successful implementation of interventions requires specialists with broad and well-developed skill sets. Many teachers need support developing this skill set through systematic professional development.

 Table 7
Performance Tracking

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Ensures the conduct of pre-reading assessment.	4.32	0.75	Strongly Agree
Ensures the weekly evaluation to monitor the student's progress.	3.82	0.88	Agree
Ensures that tools used are based on the offered intervention.	3.91	0.73	Agree
Ensures the used of Individual Learning Monitoring Plan (ILMP) to track the learner's progress.	3.80	0.80	Agree
Ensures the conduct of post-reading assessment.	4.27	0.68	Strongly Agree
Section Mean	4.02	0.64	Agree

As indicated in Table 7, the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of performance tracking got the weighted mean of 4.02 which the respondents agree on the support given by the principals with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.64$. It is also shown that the principal ensures that there were pre and post reading assessment conducted where the respondents were strongly agreed. This implies that tracking of performance of learners were actively monitored.

DepEd (2019) states that evaluations will be used to monitor students' progress, and tools based on the offered intervention. By the suggested intervention strategies, a learner's progress will be tracked using an Individual Learning Monitoring Plan (ILMP). Meanwhile, Cogendo (2023) states that the foundation of ongoing progress is performance tracking. It involves establishing precise goals, giving prompt feedback, and confidently and clearly guiding the learners to its intended destination.

Table 8
Stakeholder's Involvement

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Provides partnership activities with the PTA that are aligned with the student achievement goals.	3.95	0.80	Agree
Fortifies engagement with LGU to have an adequate learning resource, reading hubs or centers and safety environment.	3.74	0.86	Agree
Fortifies the link with the barangay officials and 4P's Program.	4.01	0.90	Agree
Actively engages with donors and sponsors and sustain resources for reading interventions.	3.75	0.88	Agree
Ensures that the stakeholders operate common values and a common vision for student achievement.	3.93	0.93	Agree
Section Mean	3.88	0.77	Agree

As described in table 8 results on the extent of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling learners in terms of Stakeholder's Involvement has a weighted mean of 3.88 described as agree with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.77$. This implies that the principal supports the involvement of stakeholders on the implementation of reading intervention program. It is shown that principals sustain the involvement of stakeholders on the implementation of reading intervention program.

Department of Education aims to bring together educators, specialists, decisionmakers, and stakeholders from all agencies to accomplish the goal which is to enhance the delivery of education (DepEd, 2019). Also, Sison and Fuentes (2025) found that stakeholder engagement plays a crucial role in improving certain aspects of school performance, especially in securing awards and recognition. They also pointed out areas where additional improvements and strategies are required to more directly connect engagement with academic outcomes.

Table 9

Summary of Principal's Support in Implementing Reading Intervention for Struggling Learners

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Time – Allocation and Scheduling	4.18	0.53	Agree
Approaches and Strategies	3.87	0.58	Agree
Information and Communication Technology Skills	4.09	0.48	Agree
Learning Resources	4.14	0.52	Agree
Teaching Material Support	3.83	0.70	Agree
Training For Teachers	4.12	0.63	Agree
Performance Tracking	4.02	0.64	Agree
Stakeholder's Involvement	3.88	0.77	Agree
Grand Mean	4.02	0.44	Agree

Table 9 presents the summary of principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program for struggling it can be observed that all indicators have an interpretation of agree with the mean of 4.02 and with a standard deviation of $\sigma=0.04$. It can be gleaned that respondents agreed that the principal supports the implementation of reading intervention program for the learners.

Park et al. (2018) suggest that principals should focus on supportive leadership to create a positive school climate, which in turn enhances teachers' behaviors and attitudes, leading to better student achievement. Manickavasagam (2018) emphasizes the significant role of principals in promoting students' reading proficiency by providing teachers with the necessary training and support to implement its program.

To answer the problem number 2, the preceding table showed the reading performance of learners.

Table 10

Reading Performance of Learners SY 2023- 2024

	Pretest		Post- test		Level
	f	%	f	%	
97 % - 100%	222	33.33	231	38.50	Independent
90% - 96%	278	41.74	262	43.67	Instructional
89% and Below	107	16.07	82	13.67	Frustration
0	59	8.86	25	4.17	Non- Reader
Total	666	100%	600	100%	

Table 10 presents the reading performance of learners in Lake Sebu Districts. During the pretest, there were two hundred seventy – eight or 41.74% of the learners who got the scores between 90 - 96 belonged to Instructional level; two hundred twenty - two or 33.33%, 97- 100, Independent level; one hundred seven or 16.07%, 89 and below, Frustration level; and fifty- nine or 8.86% identified as Non – Readers.

For the post test, two hundred sixty – two or 43.67% of the learners got a score between 90 - 96 described as Instructional level; two hundred thirty – one or 38.50%, Independent level; eighty – two or 13.67%, Frustration level and twenty – five or 4.17% were Non – Readers.

The results imply that the learners showed progress in their reading abilities, with more learners moving into the independent level and fewer in the frustration or non-reader level. While many learners have improved, majority of the learners performed below level of expectation.

Shikalepo (2020) study found that student performance in rural schools is generally unsatisfactory, with factors such as the learning foundation, teacher-to-student ratio, English proficiency, and parental involvement impacting performance. Additionally, factors like subject specialization, working conditions, genetic traits, and climate also play a role in supporting teaching and learning in rural schools.

The next research problem asks if there is a significant relationship between principal's support in implementing reading intervention program for struggling learners and their reading performance. The obtained data is presented in Table 11.

Table 11

Significant Relationship Between Principal's Support in Implementing Reading Intervention Program for Struggling Learners and their Reading Performance

Variable	R value	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
Principal Support Vs Reading Performance	-0.117	.252	Weak negative correlation	Accept H ₀

@5% level of significance

Table 11 reveals that when principal's support on the implementation of reading intervention program was correlated with the reading performance of learners, the correlation value yielded -0.117. This implies that principal's support in implementing reading intervention program is not statistically related to the reading performance of learners. It suggests that even if the principal offers strong support, it doesn't automatically lead to better reading outcomes for students. There might be other factors at play that are influencing the reading performance more directly.

Hence, the null hypothesis that states that “there is no significant relationship between principal's support on the implementation on intervention program for struggling learners and their reading performance” is accepted at level .05.

Park et al. (2018) highlight that supportive leadership is essential for enhancing teaching practices and student outcomes. They recommended that principals focus on adopting supportive

leadership styles to create a positive school climate, which can have a beneficial impact on teachers' instructional behaviors and attitudes, ultimately leading to better student performance.

However, in Shikalepo's (2020) study reveals that student performance in rural schools is unsatisfactory. The findings suggest that several factors, including the learning foundation, teacher-to-student ratio, English proficiency, and parental involvement, affect students' performance. Additionally, aspects such as subject specialization, working conditions, genetic traits, and climate also influence teaching and learning in rural schools.

To answer the problem number four (4) which asks the significant difference between pretest and post – test of the struggling learners, the preceding table showed.

Table 12

T-test Analysis on Difference Between Pretest and Post – test Reading Performance of Struggling Learners

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p	Decision
Pre-test	97	77.20	6.10	13.62	96	<.00001	Reject H ₀
Posttest	97	83.70	5.5				

Taking a look to the above table, significant difference between pretest and post - test is evident by the mean scores of 77.20 and 83.70. Thus, the second hypothesis which stated “there is no significant difference between the pretest and post-test reading performance of the struggling learners” was rejected since the t- value is 13.62. This is a very large t-value, indicating that there is an obvious improvement in the reading performance of learners. This means that there is a significant difference between the performance of learners before and after the implementation of reading intervention program.

This shows that the reading intervention has been effective in helping learners to develop their reading performance. In most educational or intervention-based studies, this implies the intervention or instruction had a significant effect. Del Mar (2023) mentioned Implementing targeted educational interventions can significantly enhance student performance and academic success.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, these conclusions are drawn: The study reveals that the extent of principal support for the implementation of the reading intervention program is generally positive, indicating agreement across various components. Time allocation and scheduling received the highest level of support, followed by learning resources, teacher training, and ICT skills, while teaching materials received the lowest support.

Despite the positive principal support across these areas, the reading performance of learners showed minimal improvement from pretest to post-test. The study found no significant relationship between the principal's support in implementing the reading intervention program and the learners' reading performance. This suggests that while principal support is essential, other factors may also influence the effectiveness of the reading intervention program on student

outcomes. Furthermore, outcome emphasizes the effectiveness of educational interventions in enhancing learners' performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Schools can further strengthen the reading intervention program and ensure that all components are at highest potential to improve student reading performance.
2. Principals may reevaluate the intervention strategies to ensure they are effective.
3. Future researchers may focus on identifying other factors that might influence the reading performance of learners. These could include the students' home environment, socio-economic background, teaching methodologies, or the availability of additional academic support services.
4. Principals may continue support the implementation of reading intervention program that fosters continuous improvement in reading skills among struggling learners.

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